

Data-driven Evaluation of Anticipatory Networking in LTE Networks

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Abstract—Anticipatory networking is a recent branch of network optimization based on prediction of the system state. Our work specifically tackles prediction-driven resource allocation for mobile networks. While some anticipatory networking concepts have been proposed in the literature, understanding of the potential real world gains is so far very limited. Future mobile networks will likely integrate such mechanisms, and thus it is of paramount importance to understand the actual performance improvements and in which scenarios they can be realized. Analyzing a month of LTE control channel information collected in four locations, we show how anticipatory networking can enhance current LTE networks. First, we propose a comprehensive optimization framework encompassing different forecasting solutions. Then, we provide a thorough analysis of the aggregated network traffic and the contributions of individual users. In particular, we show that predictable traffic accounts for more than 95% of the total traffic volume and that simple prediction and optimization techniques allow network operators to save 50% of the resources and/or on average more than double the offered data rate in our data set.

Index Terms—LTE, Prediction, Anticipatory Networking, Measurements, Optimization, Mobile Networks, Sniffer.

1 INTRODUCTION

MAX Planck once said: “the assumption of an absolute determinism is the essential foundation of every scientific enquiry” [1]. Anticipatory Networking, a recent trend in network optimization, relates to the Nobel prize winner’s aphorism by assuming that the future state of a dynamic system (i.e., the network) is, to some degree, predictable. The main difference between anticipatory and standard optimization for mobile networks is that the former explicitly uses forecasts of the network state in order to proactively address problems. In fact, the fundamental principle of anticipatory networking is that the network performance can be improved by predicting the evolution of the system. Analyzing historical data and contextual information, it is possible to model traffic dynamics at a cell-granularity [2]–[4] and to profile user behavior at different time scales [5], [6], which can be used to optimize network operations.

According to the literature, anticipatory networking solutions can improve both the network efficiency in terms of spectrum utilization and enhance the Quality-of-Service (QoS) perceived by the users (see [7] and the references therein). For example, streaming applications can rely on buffered contents to avoid using network resources when the signal quality is low and fill the buffer in the opposite situation. Knowing in advance whether the signal quality of a given user is going to improve or decrease allows the network to assign her resources when it is more efficient to do so and allows the user’s application to adapt the amount of requested data according to the predicted achievable rate. There are many more applications that can be improved by anticipatory networking. In fact, the requirements of 5G communications will push the network efficiency to its limit

and anticipatory networking is likely to become paramount to free up extra resources that will enable new applications. While anticipatory networking is a very broad concept that covers a variety of contexts (e.g., network failures and contents’ popularity), in this paper we focus on prediction-based resource allocation.

The main missing element in the whole body of work on anticipatory networking is an in-depth evaluation of the real-world performance of predictive optimization. This is due to the fact that, even though large data sets exist [8]–[10], no publicly available dataset provides mobile network information with the sufficient precision (e.g. the actual base station scheduling) and large enough to provide statistical significance. The data set closest to our requirements is the recently published MobileInsight [11] dataset. However, it consists of the logs of single users recorded independently, which therefore cannot provide the aggregate cell information obtained by our method. In this paper, we fill this gap by applying prediction-based optimization to the resource allocation data of LTE networks that we collected in four locations in Madrid over one month. In particular, we identify in the whole data set those users that are suitable to be predicted. For these, we allow their data transfers to be re-organized so that future exchanges can be anticipated (i.e., buffered) if that improves a given objective function.

In particular, in our evaluation we treat all traffic that exhibits good predictability as elastic and the rest as background traffic, which translates to a fixed and unpredictable load for the cell. Predictable traffic is then rescheduled so that the original deadlines are respected and the network performance is improved. This assumption allows us to study how the network would have performed, had it prediction capabilities. While not all predictable traffic is elastic, this is true for much of the high volume traffic such as video. The main contribution of this paper is to provide a thorough evaluation of anticipatory networking solutions using real world data. In addition, we present the tools and

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the methodology we adopted to perform our evaluation and we present the data sets as well as their characteristics. Finally, our extensive data sets are available on request for third parties to verify our conclusions and to perform their own tests.

Our analysis shows that omniscient optimizers can improve the average network efficiency by 35-40% in both communication directions, and more than double the data rate for downlink communication only. Uplink data rate can be increased by circa 8% only, because of a smaller margin of improvements. The performance obtained using realistic predictors shows that anticipatory solutions are both feasible and effective, with a performance around 5 and 10% lower than the theoretical optimum. This confirms the preliminary results obtained in the literature over synthetic data sets and the benefits that predictive optimization can bring to next generation mobile networks.

In the rest of the paper, we discuss the following novel contributions. Section 2 illustrates the comprehensive anticipatory networking framework we used to evaluate the data sets. The section provides details about 1) time series prediction, 2) linear programming formulations to minimize network resources and maximize users' data rates, and 3) the complete optimization framework that encompasses prediction accuracy and objective functions. It also explains how to proceed from data collection to performance evaluation. Section 3 discusses our measurement campaign providing 1) a summary of the LTE characteristics, 2) a short description of the data sets, and 3) a preliminary analysis on the data set where we distinguish the predictable (and thus optimizable) components from background traffic. Section 4 examines the results obtained by the different anticipatory networking techniques on the data sets and provides further considerations about them and anticipatory networking in general. Finally Sections 5 and 6 provide an analysis of the related work and our conclusions, respectively.

2 ANTICIPATORY OPTIMIZATION FRAMEWORK

Anticipatory networking solutions include two main components: prediction and optimization. Here, we limit ourselves to a few selected methods that allow us to evaluate the achievable gains due to anticipatory networking. Depending on the contextual information used and the application objectives, other solutions exist that achieve different performance. However, our methodology proved to be adequate to solve our optimization problems in very large data sets and shed some light on the actual performance of anticipatory networking solutions. For a more detailed review of possible applications and variants of these optimization solutions we refer the reader to [7].

2.1 Optimization Problem

We use a centralized decision making problem as the basis for our optimization [12], where a set \mathcal{N} of N users share a given quantity of network resources over a set \mathcal{T} of T time slots, also referred to as optimization window. The objective of our formulation is to assign the available network resources so that all users obtain the requested information while either the cost for the network is minimized or the users' data rate is maximized. In addition, both approaches

minimize the resource allocation-related service interruptions for all users. We use the following inputs for the problem characterizing users and slots with the subscripts i and j , respectively:

▷ *Predicted achievable rate* $r_{i,j} \in [0, r_M]$ is the prediction of the rate a user would achieve if no other user were scheduled. r_M is the maximum achievable data rate.

▷ *Requirement* $d_{i,j} \in [0, q_M]$ is the minimum amount of bytes needed in a given slot to stream the content at the minimum bitrate with no interruptions.

The problem is characterized by the following variables:

▷ *Resource assignment* $a_{i,j} \in [0, 1]$ represents the average fraction of resources assigned to user i in slot j . In each slot, each user can be assigned at most the total available rate, $0 \leq a_{i,j} \leq 1$, and the sum cannot exceed the total available resources, $0 \leq \sum_{i \in \mathcal{N}} a_{i,j} \leq 1$.

▷ *Buffer state* $b_{i,j} \in [0, b_M]$ tracks the amount of bytes stored in the buffer and b_M is the buffer size in bytes.

▷ *Outage* $l_{i,j} \in [0, q_M]$ is the missing data to fulfill the minimum content requirement $d_{i,j}$:

$$l_{i,j} = [d_{i,j} - b_{i,j} - a_{i,j}r_{i,j}]_0^{d_{i,j}} \quad (1)$$

where $[x]_a^b = \min\{\max\{x, a\}, b\}$ is a bounding operator that forces the undelivered quantity to be greater than zero and smaller than the requirement in the slot.

In each slot j user i receives $a_{i,j}r_{i,j}$ bits (i.e., the corresponding fraction of the data rate of a time slot), which can be used either to satisfy the requirements in the current slot or to fill the buffer for later use. Thus we can write the following equation that describes the next buffer state:

$$b_{i,j+1} = b_{i,j} + a_{i,j}r_{i,j} - d_{i,j} + l_{i,j}. \quad (2)$$

We define $b_{i,0}$ as the initial status of the buffer of user i .

In addition, we introduce three metrics that we will use to build the objective function for our problem. Namely, we define the amount of used resources $\delta_i = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{T}} a_{i,k}$, the fraction of continuous service time $\lambda_i = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{T}} (1 - l_{i,k}d'_{i,k})$ and the fraction of the extra data rate obtained $\theta_i = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{T}} (a_{i,k}r_{i,k}d'_{i,k} - 1)$, where we use $d'_{i,j} = 1/d_{i,j}$ if $d_{i,j} > 0$ and 0 otherwise to avoid division by zero.

Finally, we build two objective functions: the first minimizes the network resources spent, while the second maximizes the overall delivered data. Both objective functions must guarantee minimum outage before tackling the specific objective: if resources are not sufficient to satisfy the minimum requirements, both functions will give the same resulting allocation, which minimizes the overall outage. For the **resource minimization** we obtain the following LP formulation:

$$\underset{A,B,L}{\text{minimize}} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{N}} (\delta_k - K\lambda_k) \quad (3)$$

$$\text{subject to: } a_{i,j} \geq 0; \quad \sum_{k \in \mathcal{N}} a_{k,j} \leq 1 - a_{B,j}$$

$$l_{i,j} \geq 0; \quad b_{i,j} \leq b_M$$

$$l_{i,j} \geq d_{i,j} - a_{i,j}r_{i,j} - b_{i,j}$$

$$\forall i \in \mathcal{N}; j \in \mathcal{T}$$

where the weight K ensures that the solver's priority is on outage minimization¹ and $a_{B,j}$ represents the fraction of resources used by background traffic at time j . Background traffic is the fraction of load that cannot be predicted nor optimized, because it originates from real-time or inelastic sources (e.g. chat and online gaming). Operators and users can distinguish the two types of traffic (e.g., by the bearer used to carry them or by the app); we will show in Section 3.4 how to compute $a_{B,j}$ in our case. The **data rate maximization** LP is given by:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \text{maximize} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{N}} (\theta_k + K \lambda_k) & (4) \\
 & \text{subject to: } a_{i,j} \geq 0; \sum_{k \in \mathcal{N}} a_{k,j} \leq 1 - a_{B,j} \\
 & \sum_{k \in \mathcal{T}} a_{i,k} \leq a_{i,0}; \quad l_{i,j} \geq 0; \quad b_{i,j} \leq b_M \\
 & l_{i,j} \geq d_{i,j} - a_{i,j} r_{i,j} - b_{i,j} \\
 & \forall i \in \mathcal{N}; j \in \mathcal{T}
 \end{aligned}$$

where $a_{i,0}$ is an upper limit on the total resources assigned to user i . Formally, the two optimization problems should use mixed-integer formulations, because LTE resources are only assignable in finite quantities. However, since the time slots used for our optimization are two orders of magnitude longer than the LTE Transmission Time Interval (TTI), the expected approximation error is smaller than 1%.

2.2 Prediction Methodology

Among the many prediction techniques, we opt for time-series analysis, because it is simple to implement, to train and its computational complexity is sufficiently low. Here, we make no attempt to compare different prediction schemes and we do not claim the superiority of the methods used here compared to other solutions. Our objective is to show a feasible solution that can be easily adopted in current networks. In addition, we evaluate the impact of prediction errors on the optimization quality.

According to previous optimization solutions [12]–[14], we need to predict users' achievable data rates, because knowing the maximum data rate all users can be assigned at any given time is required to optimize the resource allocation process. Although many parameters impact on users' achievable rates [7], not all of them are consistently available for all devices (e.g. GPS position) and might not be accessible to network operators (e.g. precise location, speed), in our measurement campaign we collect and study Modulation and Coding Scheme (MCS) together with the resources assigned to all the users. In fact, achievable rate is a function of MCS obtained using LTE tables [15] and is directly available to both users and operators.

We adopt AutoRegressive Integrative Moving Average (ARIMA) time-series analysis to model each of the users and, subsequently, we use the obtained models to evaluate the prediction Mean Square Error (MSE). Since ARIMA models require the time-series to have equidistant samples in time, before applying the model we regularize our data: first, we analyze the average MCS over time bins and,

1. Ideally, K should be infinite, but in practice a large enough value (e.g. $K = 10^6$) is sufficient to ensure the optimization order.

Fig. 1. Two examples of data series captured with MobileInsight showing different level of smoothing.

Fig. 2. Cumulative Density Function of the error introduced by interpolating over gaps of varying size.

then, we linearly interpolate our series over gaps longer than one bin duration (i.e., when a given series contains no information over a period longer than a bin). We fix the bin duration to 200 ms which allows reliable achievable rate estimation [16] while preserving the MCS variability induced by user mobility. In addition, the selected bin duration should be long enough to filter fast MCS variation due to fast fading in most scenarios. This binning technique is only used to create the predictor filters, while the rest of the optimization is performed on the actual data series.

To verify the impact of linear interpolation over unknown gaps, we test it over very dense data series collected with MobileInsight [11] and we create gaps to be filled by linear interpolation. The test series are recorded either while walking at a regular pace or during car rides in the city center. In both scenarios the tested mobile phone is constantly receiving a video in order to ensure a dense log (i.e., very frequent communications). Fig. 1 shows two examples of the vehicular and pedestrian mobility effect on the MCS variation. Both figures show instantaneous samples (gray dots) and the effect of smoothing of different sizes (lines). Our tests, which are summarized in Fig. 2, show that the error caused by linear interpolation is usually smaller than 5%, increasing substantially (max. 15%) only for long gaps and vehicular mobility.

While the true rate variation during information gaps is

Fig. 3. Average normalized prediction error.

unknown, linear interpolation is the most viable approach to analyze our data set without resorting to very complex mathematical models that would require excessive computation time for our very large data sets. In addition, we expect the users of the selected locations to exhibit either a pedestrian or a slow vehicular mobility, both of which can be approximate with linear mobility over time intervals as short as the ones found in our data series.

An ARIMA model is characterized by three parameters: the autoregressive order p , the moving average order q and the degree of differencing d . For each of the data series, we choose the best orders for the ARIMA model according to the Box-Jenkins [17] methodology. Then, we estimate the model coefficients by means of least square regression. Note that we create a model for each of the data series using all the information available. This allows to evaluate the best possible prediction obtainable with this methodology.

In a real system, it might be impossible to have separate predictors for each user, and general models associated to user profiles might be used instead. Fig. 3 shows the average predictor error normalized to the standard deviation and averaged over five thousand logs in our datasets. Clearly, the prediction error rapidly increases in the first few seconds and exceeds half of the standard deviation after 10 seconds. This motivates the limit on the prediction horizon that we will use in Section 4.

2.3 Evaluation Framework

In the previous parts of this section we defined our prediction and optimization tools. We remark that the reasons for our choices were mainly twofold: 1) test optimality (with perfect prediction and LP optimization) against suboptimal and more realistic options and 2) control the computational complexity to evaluate them on our data set. In particular, we define the following features.

We include three levels of prediction accuracy:

- ▷ *Perfect*: the exact achievable rates are fed to the optimizer.
- ▷ *Proactive*: the prediction is computed by feeding the ARIMA models defined above with all the past samples of the data series. Since the optimizer can accurately know a given user achievable rate only when that user is actively using the medium, this type of prediction requires some sort of active achievable rate measurements when the user is not scheduled.
- ▷ *Reactive*: past information is only updated when the user is scheduled. To feed the optimizer with a continuous series we fill the gaps by linear interpolation and we continue

Fig. 4. A comparison between the solutions obtained with perfect and realistic predictors.

to generate new predictions until a new scheduling event happens.

Note that, as a consequence of our optimization scheme, some communication events may happen at different instants or not happen at all. Thus, the main difference between the proactive and the reactive predictors is that the former can use all the past data in the series independently of their actual usage, while the latter is only fed with information when users are effectively scheduled after the optimization. In such a way, reactive predictors can only use a subset of the information available to proactive ones, whereas the latter imply active measurement to infer the feasible MCS.

To illustrate the impact of prediction uncertainty, Fig. 4 shows a detailed comparison between a solution obtained by the ideal optimizer (solid black line) and one using the reactive prediction (dashed blue line). Both lines show the total data transferred, while the shaded area represents the downlink achievable rate. While the ideal solution only transfers data when the achievable rate is maximum, the solution adopting a reactive predictor cannot take full advantage of the best conditions because they happen too suddenly to be predicted accurately. We remark that transmitting when the achievable rate is higher means using a higher MCS and, thus, transmitting more data with the same time resources.

We analyze two objective functions:

- ▷ *Resource Minimization*: we use the problem definition of Eq. 3 to compute the minimum amount of resources needed to provide each active user in the system with the same total rate they obtained in the original data set. We enforce causality, by allowing users to use resources in the past to satisfy requirements in the future, but not vice versa.
- ▷ *Quality Maximization*: we use the problem definition of Eq. 4 to compute the maximum data rate that could be obtained by each active user in the system exploiting the same total quantity of resources. The parameter $a_{i,0}$ is set to match the resource quantity before the optimization.

We consider two optimization types to compare operator- and user-driven anticipatory networking:

- ▷ *Centralized*: the two problem formulations above are already defined as centralized problem were a common solver uses all the available information to compute the best resource allocation. This type is likely to be implemented on base station and controlled by a mobile operator.
- ▷ *Distributed*: in a distributed scheme each user optimize her

behavior (i.e., the amount of requested data) according to her limited view of the system. The problem formulation is the same as for the centralized type, but it is repeated for each user individually. This type of optimization is suitable to be implemented in mobile phone applications to allow user-driven optimization that can be deployed independently of the mobile operator.

The main difference between these two types is that centralized optimization cannot generate infeasible conditions, while the distributed type might create allocations overflows: this condition happens when a number of users decide to request data in the same time slot and their combined request is larger than the available resources. This is avoided in the centralized approach, by bounding the total request at any given time, but cannot be avoided in the distributed version, because users are not aware of other users decisions. When an infeasible allocation is decided, we normalize the requests proportionally and we adjust all the remaining parameters accordingly. However, by doing so, the users receive less than what requested and this may cause an interruption in the service being offered. By comparing the two approaches, we can evaluate whether it is more efficient for the operators to maintain the full control of the optimization process or if moving the complexity from base stations to mobile phones can be a feasible alternative.

In order to apply our evaluation framework on real data we proceed as follows: 1) Collect LTE scheduling information: we describe the tools we use and the locations where we perform the measurements. 2) Identify the predictable fraction of the traffic: active users exhibits characteristic features that help us distinguishing their data from background/passive traffic. 3) Apply our evaluation framework on the data sets.

3 LTE MEASUREMENTS

We performed a one month measurement campaign in four LTE cells in Madrid in which we used our Online Watcher for LTE (OWL) [18], a decoder of the LTE control channel. OWL uses a software-defined radio (SDR) to sample the LTE downlink channel and implements the decoding functionalities based on srsLTE [19], an open-source LTE library.

LTE scheduling measurements are possible because of centralized communication management and unencrypted control channel information. Centralized communications imply that a single base station (eNodeB) coordinates the data transfers of the mobile phones, also known as user equipments (UEs), in both downlink and uplink channels. In particular, the eNodeB sends scheduling information to UEs using a dedicated channel. Thanks to our sniffer we are able to decode from the control channel the following information: 1) temporary user ID (C-RNTI) that does not allow to uniquely identify the user, but is sufficient to follow the scheduling of a given user over time until she stops her communications for longer than 10 seconds or she changes the cell, 2) assigned MCS, 3) allocated number of resource blocks, 4) transport block size.

In addition to long lasting measurements, OWL can be used as an online tool for network traffic visualization as shown in Fig. 5. This figure includes a BladeRF x40 [20] on the left hand side and a laptop running the software

Fig. 5. OWL configuration as an online network traffic visualizer. The SDR is placed on the left, while the laptop runs the main software and the visualizations are shared between the laptop (used resources and data rates) and the monitor (spectrogram).

on the right. In this configurations, the laptop's monitor is showing the evolution of the used resources (bottom charts) and the achieved data rates (top charts) for the uplink and downlink channels (left and right charts, respectively). On the external monitor we visualize the received power over time (vertical axis) and frequency (horizontal axis). This is just but an example of OWL's capabilities that can be easily extended starting from the software provided at: https://git.networks.imdea.org/nicola_bui/imdeaowl. In what follows we provide some basic details on the LTE control channel and our sniffer.

3.1 LTE Control Channel Details

The main characteristics that make LTE scheduling measurements possible are two: centralized communication management and unencrypted control channel information. In particular, the eNodeB sends scheduling information to UEs using the Physical Downlink Control Channel (PDCCH), to send Downlink Control Information (DCI) messages. In what follows we provide some basic details to understand the principles of decoding LTE control channel. We refer the interested reader to [15], [21], [22] for further information.

Fig. 6 shows a spectrogram of 5 subframes of a 10 MHz LTE signal. Each subframe lasts 1 ms and corresponds to the one LTE TTI. The grid represents 50 resource blocks horizontally and 5 subframes (70 symbols) vertically. The PDCCH occupies the first few symbols in each subframe and it is highlighted in red in the figure. In addition, the figure shows the location of the primary and secondary synchronization sequences (PSS and CSS) that repeat every 5 ms and the master information block (MIB) repeated every 10 ms. Finally, the different shades of gray refer to the average power measured on the resource blocks: the lighter the color, the higher the received power. We marked two transmissions in subframes 0 and 2 and an interfering communication in subframe 1.

DCIs use Radio Network Temporary Identifiers (RNTIs) to specify their destination. RNTIs are 16-bit identifiers that can assume different roles in LTE. Among them, only two are relevant for our concerns: random access RNTI (RA-RNTI) and cell RNTI (C-RNTI). The former only takes values in $[1 - 10]$ and is used during the random access procedure to allow the eNodeB to address an unknown UE. The latter can take any unreserved value in $[0x003D - FFF3]$ and is assigned to the UE by the eNodeB at the end of the random access procedure.

Fig. 6. Snapshot of the LTE downlink channel highlighting used resource blocks and the control channel locations.

A brief overview of the random access procedure is as follows: 1) the UE sends one out of 64 possible preambles (Zadoff-Chu sequences) in subframe i ; 2) the eNodeB sends a Random Access Response (RAR) message in which a temporary C-RNTI is assigned to the UE; 3) the UE sends a Radio Resource Control (RRC) connection request message; 4) the eNodeB responds with contention resolution message to the UE. In order for the UE to receive the RAR, the related DCI is sent to the RA-RNTI address $i + 1$, which is defined by the subframe where the UE sent the preamble. The C-RNTI received during step 2 is only confirmed in step 4; in fact, if two or more UEs selects the same subframe for sending the preamble, all of them receive the RAR with the same information. However, only one of them will successfully complete step 3, thus, receiving the final confirmation from the eNodeB. In any case, the temporary C-RNTI sent in the RAR is assigned to one of the users participating in the random access procedure.

Note that the DCI sent to the RA-RNTI only carries information for the UE to decode the RAR, which is sent in the shared downlink channel. Thus, after decoding the RAR, the UE is informed about the time alignment, the upload grant to send the connection request and the C-RNTI.

DCI messages specify whether they are related to uplink or downlink communications. DCIs carrying scheduling information always specify the Modulation and Coding Scheme (MCS) as a 5-bit field that determines the modulation and the code rate that will be used in the corresponding transmission. The last two pieces of information that are relevant to our analysis are the number of used resource blocks N_{RB}^2 and the transport block size. The definition of the former depends on the actual DCI format, while the latter is derived by using MCS and N_{RB} as indices in a lookup table. The complete definitions can be found in [21]. Finally, DCI messages have a CRC footer, which is the result of a XOR operation between the CRC computed over the DCI payload and the C-RNTI of the destination UE.

3.2 OWL: Main Features and Performance

OWL is a control channel decoder for LTE. Here, we describe its main component, while the interested reader is referred to our workshop paper [18] for the details. OWL inherits from srsLTE the basic synchronization and decoding functions, such as CFI decoding, channel equalization and mapping. On top of this, OWL extends the srsLTE library to perform a blind (i.e., without prior knowledge) decoding

2. The load $a_{i,j}$ in our framework is expressed as the average fraction of used N_{RB} .

Fig. 7. A comparison between the performance of OWL and LTEye.

of all possible locations of the PDCCH. In particular, while a single UE can monitor a limited set of control channel locations, OWL needs to extend the procedure to all possible locations and DCI formats.

If a communication is detected on the PDCCH, the decoding procedure is performed for all possible DCI formats. A normal UE considers the decoding operation successful if the CRC field, scrambled with the CRC computed on the data, matches its C-RNTI. However, OWL needs to decode DCIs addressed to all the active UEs, but does not know their C-RNTIs in advance. Thus, it must populate and maintain a list of the active C-RNTIs at any given time.

To populate this C-RNTI list, OWL has two options: 1) intercepting the random access procedure and decoding the RAR, and 2) verifying the successful decoding of a DCI message by re-encoding it and comparing the results with the symbols received over the channel. The first option is possible, because RAR messages are specified using a DCI whose CRC is XORed with a RA-RNTI. When this happens, OWL can decode the RAR message itself, by decoding the specified RBs using the given MCS. Since the RAR message contains a 24-bit parity check, it is also possible to verify whether the decoding is correct. LTE RRC messages are coded using ASN.1 [23], but RAR messages can only assume one of a given set of configurations that, in turn, carry the C-RNTI in specific and fixed positions.

The second option that implies the DCI re-encoding is inherited from LTEye [24], one of the first attempts in LTE control channel decoding. This procedure is mainly used to bootstrap the list for those C-RNTIs that were assigned before the logging started and to recover in case of missed random access procedures in the unlikely event of lack of synchronization. Implementing both approaches allowed us to ensure OWL high decoding robustness.

C-RNTIs are just temporary identifiers and, after a complete SFN cycle (10.24 seconds) of inactivity, a UE needs to perform the access procedure again to obtain a new one. For this reason, OWL resets all the RNTIs in the list that are inactive for more than a SFN cycle. Finally, while OWL uses the LTEye re-encoding procedure to bootstrap the RNTI list, at steady state we verified that OWL effectively detects all new RNTIs assigned by the eNodeB. As such, we only enable the DCI re-encoding when OWL detects a DCI message whose CRC is not XORed with a C-RNTI in the active list. This makes OWL both robust, because of the actual decoding verification, and computationally effective, because unnecessary re-encoding operations are avoided.

To evaluate and compare the performance of OWL and LTEye, we, first, recorded 100 logs of 10 seconds each at

Fig. 8. Maps of the four locations of the measurement campaign highlighting the positions of the sniffer and the base station.

TABLE 1
Dataset Statistics

	Callao	Rastro	IMDEA	Leganes
Operator	Movistar	Vodafone	Vodafone	Yoigo
Bandwidth	15 MHz	10 MHz	10 MHz	10 MHz
Frequency	1.8 GHz	800 MHz	800 MHz	1.8 GHz
Data Set Size	60 GB	19 GB	4 GB	24 GB
Total Time	35.5 days	37.5 days	21.3 days	18.7 days
Total Download	4.5 PB	0.86 PB	1.1 PB	0.15 PB
Total Upload	1.5 PB	0.3 PB	0.43 PB	0.02 PB
Total Traces	10.8 M	1 M	1.45 M	0.16 M
Active Traces	3.7 M	0.4 M	0.52 M	0.08 M
Med. D. Load	5 %	1 %	2.5 %	0.1 %
Med. D. Rate	1.13 Mbps	0.04 Mbps	0.24 Mbps	0.01 Mbps
Max D. Rate	21.3 Mbps	19.5 Mbps	22.2 Mbps	6 Mbps
A. Med. D. Rate	12.2 Mbps	12 Mbps	9.6 Mbps	14.1 Mbps
A. Max D. Rate	110 Mbps	75 Mbps	75 Mbps	75 Mbps
Med. U. Load	2.5 %	1 %	3 %	0.05 %
Med. U. Rate	0.36 Mbps	0.06 Mbps	0.16 Mbps	5 Kbps
Max U. Rate	18 Mbps	12 Mbps	12.3 Mbps	4.9 Mbps
A. Med. U. Rate	4.8 Mbps	2.7 Mbps	2.7 Mbps	2.3 Mbps
A. Max U. Rate	55 Mbps	37 Mbps	37 Mbps	37 Mbps

different time of the day. Then, we computed the number of resource blocks used in each subframe of the recorded logs by comparing the average received power in a resource block with the received power of the reference signals surrounding it. Finally, we decoded the logs with OWL and for each DCI we verified it by re-encoding the message and comparing it to the received signal. If the two differ for less than 2% of the bits we count the message as a valid decoding for LTEye.

Fig. 7 shows the fraction of RBs detected by OWL and LTEye compared to those detected by the verifier in each frame. We group the results in bars that show in the ordinate the probability to successfully decode a given fraction of RBs (x -axis) for the two solutions. In all figures the x -axis is modified in order to highlight where the probability distributions concentrate. OWL correctly decodes the 99.95% of the frames. Conversely, LTEye only decodes 90% of the RBs on average.

3.3 Campaign description

Our measurement campaign consists of the data collected by OWL during one month in four different locations. We selected the four locations in order to analyze how optimization methods would perform in areas with different uses (e.g. residential, commercial, offices, education, etc.). In particular, we monitor two locations in Madrid and two in Leganes, a smaller town nearby. In the following, we will refer to them as *Callao*, *Rastro*, *Leganes* and *IMDEA*. Overall, we collected more than 100 GB of LTE scheduling information, corresponding to a total amount of 8860 terabytes of transferred data in the four locations.

The city locations in Madrid are close to the city center and they are characterized by a high density of commercial

activity, while the locations in Leganes are more residential. Although all four locations include both pedestrian and vehicular mobility patterns, the average users' speed in the city center is expected to be lower than that in Leganes. In all locations eNodeBs are placed on top of buildings of about four floors of height, except for Callao where the buildings are taller.

Table 1 provides statistical information of the four data sets. Although all the locations show a hourly low median load of less than 5%, in all of them the median over 5 minutes reached peaks as high as 70% of the available resources.

Callao – The first measurement area is located in Madrid downtown, along the path of the most central shopping and restaurant street, Gran Via. Fig. 8(a) shows the sniffer and the eNodeB positions in a map of the surroundings. The area surrounding the eNodeB location is one of the main squares of the city. The sniffer is located at the second floor of the building directly facing the square and without any direct obstacle between it and the eNodeB. The LTE signal received in this location belongs to Telefonica (Movistar) and is in the 1.8 GHz band with a bandwidth of 15 MHz. Mobile users in this area are either pedestrians walking in the square or vehicles driving in the main street crossing the map in the horizontal direction. Given the location and type of the area, the mobile network traffic should be concentrated between late morning and midnight, but some traffic should be present at any time.

Rastro – The second location is a market area of Madrid and takes its name from “el rastro”, the most famous flea market of the city. This is still a central area, but not quite as crowded as Callao. Fig. 8(b) provides information about sniffer and eNodeB locations and the commercial activities in the surroundings. The eNodeB location is on the roof of a short building on the corner of the crossroad, while the sniffer is placed in the third floor of an apartment in the nearby square. Although there is no direct line of sight between the two, the sniffer obtained a sufficiently high signal strength to decode the control channel. In the surrounding of the eNodeB, most of the commercial activities are either restaurants or small shops. The central area between the sniffer and the eNodeB is the market square. The crowd in the surroundings is mainly pedestrian or slowly moving vehicles. Here, we received a 10 MHz signal from Vodafone in the 800 MHz.

IMDEA – The third location is in Leganes, a town nearby Madrid, where our research center is placed. Fig. 8(c) provides information about sniffer and eNodeB locations. The eNodeB location is on the roof of a building within a residential area. We placed the sniffer in one of IMDEA's

Fig. 9. CDF of the trace duration mapped to the sorted CDF of load and data rate in Callao.

meeting rooms so that the LTE antennas are in line of sight of the sniffer. As a consequence, we obtained a very high received signal strength. Since the area is mainly residential, we expect the majority of the people to use private WiFi communication. The same is true for the office employees of the school, mall, and bank nearby. However, we expect a higher level of traffic during commuting time and when parents drive children to school. The LTE signal received in this location belongs to Vodafone, it is in the 800 MHz band and has a bandwidth of 10 MHz.

Leganes – The fourth and last location is in the center of Leganes as shown in Fig. 8(d). The eNodeB location is on the roof of a building facing the main street of the area. We placed the sniffer behind the window of a balcony in the direction of the eNodeB. A direct line of sight was not available, though, and the signal strength was just above the threshold required to decode the signal. Also this area is mainly residential with a few commercial activities in the surroundings. The LTE signal received in this location belongs to Yoigo, it is in the 1.8 GHz band and has a bandwidth of 10 MHz.

3.4 Dataset Analysis

In our data sets, users are identified by their RNTI, temporary identifiers used in LTE control channel. Each user is associated with a trace containing an entry for each scheduling event and an entry is characterized by the absolute time in milliseconds, the number of assigned resource blocks, the MCS used, the transport block size and the communication direction (downlink or uplink). Since a user maintains her RNTI as long as she is active with no pause longer than 10 seconds, we split the traces accordingly: whenever a gap of 10 seconds or longer is present in a trace, it is split in two parts. Thus, we can analyze each trace in isolation and collect statistics about per user network usage. In particular, each trace is a list of scheduling events concerning a particular user containing:

- absolute time in milliseconds (LTE TTI)
- communication direction (downlink or uplink)
- $MCS \in [0, 31]$ (related to the achievable rate)
- N_{RB} (from which we derive the load)
- transport block size (actual data rate)

For each collected trace we compute a set of compound metrics. The first three of them are trace duration, downlink

Fig. 10. MCS comparison for active and all users for both downlink and uplink.

trace size and uplink trace size. We first note that more than 60% of the collected traces are shorter than 10 seconds and are smaller than 1.25 KByte in terms of transferred data. This means that the majority of the collected traces carries little information. We assume that these (small) traces belong to background traffic performed by mobile phones without any active intervention from the user or are related to automatic network management operations³.

We analyze this in more details by computing the contribution to the total load of the traces longer than a given threshold or traces that transferred more than a given size of information. Fig. 9 shows the trace duration CDF as a black solid line and maps the CDFs of the users' downlink load and total transferred size to their trace duration as dashed blue and dash-dotted red lines, respectively, for the Callao data set.

The two CDFs represent the total load and data rate for all those users whose trace is longer than the value on the x-axis or, in other words, for a given duration on the x-axis, the three curves represent the fraction of traces shorter than that and the corresponding fraction of the total load and the total data transferred, respectively. Thus, traces shorter than 20s (dotted vertical line), which account for about three quarters of the total traces (black line) constitute 20% of the total load (blue dashed line). A similar behavior can be found when analyzing the transferred data size compared to the total load and it is valid for both downlink and uplink and for all the data sets.

Our next consideration is that short or small traces are not relevant to the objectives of anticipatory networking. They are difficult to use for Quality-of-Service (QoS) improvements, because they introduce little traffic and are difficult to predict due to their short length.

Fig. 10 shows the CDF of downlink (black) and uplink (blue) average MCS for all (dashed) and active (solid) users. Here we define a user to be active if its trace is either longer than 20 seconds or the transferred data size (either downlink or uplink) is larger than 12.5 KByte. Note that this size corresponds to the size of a thumbnail image or that of a post of a messaging application.

3. In addition, whenever communication with a UE is interrupted without proper termination, the base station verifies the UEs status by assigning a further upload grant 10 seconds after the last communication. Thus, such communications appear with a duration of around 10 seconds or more, whereas the actual communication until the interrupt may have been shorter.

Fig. 11. (Left) CDF of standard deviation of the MCS used in active traces; (Right) Absolute variation of the MCS.

Both downlink and uplink CDF show that active users have a higher average MCS, but also that downlink and uplink MCS distributions are quite different. The higher average MCS of active users is relevant for our analysis and shows that it is more likely for a user to be scheduled if she has a better signal quality, in case a larger volume of traffic is transmitted. However, the difference between downlink and uplink distributions, even though interesting per se, it is not directly relevant to the evaluation of anticipatory optimization. In fact, we believe this is mainly due to frequency division duplex: LTE networks have the uplink band at a lower frequency range to allow mobile terminals to save energy and this also provides a better signal quality due to the lower path loss.

Now that we defined active users/traces and their contributions, we address cell aggregated results computed for all users compared to the contribution of active users only. A user's achievable rate is a function of the assigned MCS, which, in turn, is a function of the path loss (i.e., Channel Quality Indicator (CQI)) and the error probability. Before evaluating the performance of prediction techniques for the collected traces, we analyze the MCS statistics and their variation over time. In particular, we evaluate for each active user, the following metrics: average, median, standard deviation, range, standard deviation of the binned average, average binned standard deviation, and average absolute variation of the binned MCS.

While the first four metrics are standard statistics obtained for the whole trace, the last three metrics are obtained by evaluating the traces over bins of equal duration. For each bin of a trace we compute the average MCS and its standard deviation. The overall idea is that the average MCS should be linked to the average path loss or signal quality experienced by the user, while the standard deviation should be linked to fast signal quality variations (i.e., fading). Thus, by evaluating these metrics over the whole trace and over bins, we characterize traces in terms of signal quality, noisiness and their variation over time.

Ideally, for a trace to be easily predictable, it should have a low noisiness and low quality variation. Fig. 11 (left) shows the CDF of the MCS standard deviation in the four data sets, which is consistently smaller than 6 which means the range of MCS variation is usually modest, but can be quite high in some cases. For instance, the Callao data set shows the highest noise, which can be a consequence of the particular topology of the area. Fig. 11 (right) shows the CDF

of the average absolute variation of the binned MCS, which measures how fast the MCS varies in subsequent bins. This tells us that the traces in the data set have a slow to medium dynamic with successive MCS changes around 2-3 (max. range 28), which means that rapid large variations in MCS are not common. As a consequence, the ARIMA predictors can be effectively applied on our data set to model and predict the MCS trends.

4 EVALUATION AND DISCUSSION

In this section we investigate the performance of the different optimization approaches and degrees of prediction accuracy. We analyze the improvement obtainable with respect to the normal mobile network behavior, which is the baseline for our test. In addition, accounting for omniscient and realistic predictors we obtain the feasible region for other existing solutions. To evaluate our framework, we proceed by selecting small portions of the data sets. Fig. 12 provides an example of a 35-second analysis of the downlink channel, containing 45 active users. The top chart shows the evolution of the MCS for all the active users in the time frame, where each user is represented by a separate row and the color varies from white (no communication), to light blue (bad channel quality, few Kbps) fading into red (good channel quality, tens of Mbps). The bottom chart, instead shows aggregate information about the cell traffic: the average total load is shown as a solid black line and the contribution to the load generated by background traffic as a dashed red line.

Each portion of the data set is generated as follows:

- select a subset of the data set of length T and starting at time τ
- identify all N active users in the subset and retrieve their MCS traces
- create the ground truth elements $r_{i,j}$ from the MCS traces using the tables in the standard [15] to compute the transport block size for the maximum number of resource blocks. The ground truth is created for $i \in [1, N]$ and $j \in [\tau - \Delta_T, T + \Delta_T]$, where Δ_T is a margin to remove boundary effects from the evaluation⁴.

4. The Δ_T margin allows to initialize models for long lasting traces that have been cut to fit in the analyzed slice (in the beginning) and provide some information for the models of the traces that started in the final part of the slice (at the end).

Fig. 12. A 35-second portion of the downlink channel of the Callao data set. Each row of the top chart shows the MCS evolutions of an active user. The lower chart provide aggregated information of the cell traffic.

- create ARIMA models and proactive predictions for all N users
- create minimum requirements $d_{i,j}$ and used resources $a_{i,0}$ as the amount of exchanged traffic and used resources, respectively
- create the background load $a_{B,j}$ for $j \in [\tau - \Delta_T, \tau + T + \Delta_T]$ summing the load of all non-active users
- run all the optimization schemes and compute their performance on the central time span $j \in [\tau, \tau + T]$. We refer to the resource allocation computed by the optimizer as $a_{i,j}^*$.

Thus, for each analyzed time span we obtain the resource saving percentage as $\frac{100}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \left(1 - \sum_{j=\tau}^{\tau+T} a_{i,j}^*/a_{i,0}\right)$, the data rate increase percentage as $\frac{100}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \left(\sum_{j=\tau}^{\tau+T} a_{i,j}^* r_{i,j}/d_{i,0} - 1\right)$ and the total outage as $\sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=\tau}^{\tau+T} l_{i,j}^*$.

Due to the intrinsic computational complexity of the problem that entails training ARIMA predictors and solving several multi-objective LP systems, it was not feasible to apply a brute force method to evaluate the results over every single portion of the four data sets. Instead, we opted for exploring the data sets in order to cover their characteristics uniformly. During the aggregated information analysis, we also associated each analyzed data set portion to its average characteristics. For instance, load, MCS and prediction error statistics qualify each slice in terms of traffic quantity and trace predictability. Then, we computed the statistic distributions of these characteristics in the data sets to obtain bins such that the same fraction of the total load falls in each of them. Finally, we select the next portion of the data set to analyze from the bin that contains the fewest samples. In such a way, we can assess the impact of the different features of the data set on the performance of the anticipatory networking techniques.

In addition, we assume that each active user's traffic can be re-organized as if it were generated by a multimedia streaming application: future data transfers can be buffered as soon as the trace starts and up to the maximum buffer size. When not specified otherwise, the buffer is assumed to be infinite, which gives an upper bound on the performance. Finally, while ideal methods are computed at once on each analyzed portion of the data set, realistic methods are iteratively updated in each time slot to recompute predictions and re-evaluate the solution of the optimization framework.

Fig. 13. Variation of the ideal optimizer performance over a full day of downlink traffic in Callao, compared to the cell load. Lines illustrate the moving averages of the parameters, while dots are single results.

We start with the performance of the ideal resource minimization optimizer with perfect future knowledge over a whole day. Fig. 13 illustrates as a solid black line the average resource percentage saved over 30-minute moving windows. Grey dots represents single results computed over time spans of $T = 10$ seconds with $\Delta_T = 5$ seconds. The red dashed line illustrates the cell load variation averaged over 30-minute moving windows. The figure is obtained for the downlink channel of the Callao data set.

First of all, the average performance of the resource minimization solution is very good. In fact, the solution is able to maintain an average saving almost always higher than 30% and up to 45%. However, the instantaneous performance of the solution is much more variable and spans the whole possible range from 0% (no improvement) to about 65%. These extreme conditions happen more frequently when the load of the cell is very low and, thus, they are symptoms of critical conditions in the analyzed portion of the data set: such as a single active user whose trace is either already optimal (for 0%) or it allows for very high saving ($> 55\%$). For what concerns the impact of the cell load on the optimization performance, we cannot determine any strong correlation by visual inspection. However, the range of individual results is wider for low load, while it gets smaller when the load is higher. When the cell load is higher, there are also more active users in the cell and the overall characteristic tends towards the average condition of the cell, while when the load is low, the individual behavior of each user dominates the aggregate characteristic of the

Fig. 14. CDFs of the resource saving and the outage obtained by anticipatory networking solutions for different prediction accuracies and for centralized and distributed schemes.

cell traffic and determines the system performance.

Fig. 14(a) shows the CDFs of the downlink resource saving performance obtained by the three prediction accuracy levels (perfect, proactive and reactive)⁵. The strongest impact on the system optimization is caused by replacing the perfect knowledge by more realistic approaches. Also, the chosen realistic approach does not strongly affect the amount of saved resources. A close inspection (see the zooms in the lower right part of the figures) allows to see the difference between the reactive and proactive predictions. Although they fare very similarly, the figures show that some higher resource savings are obtained by the reactive approach. This result might seem counter-intuitive, but is justified examining the other metric: the outage, which is shown in Fig. 14(b). In fact, while the centralized scheme never suffers from any outage, the distributed one does and, although the continuous service metric $\lambda \sim 1$ (i.e., the sum of the unsatisfied requirements is consistently smaller than $1 \text{ ms} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{N}, j \in \mathcal{T}} l_{i,j} \leq 10^{-3}$), it is sufficient to allow the optimizer to achieve some extra resource savings.

Overall the performance degradation due to realistic prediction methods ranges from 5-10% for high savings (> 40%), to 10-15% for moderate savings (20-40%) to more than 15% for low savings. Even though this last condition happens in fewer than 15% of the analyzed cases, these are the cases where anticipatory networking is more likely to be useless or detrimental to the users' QoS: in fact, while some resources are still saved, they might be saved at the expenses of some outage, which will impact the users' experience.

The performance of centralized and distributed optimization schemes (solid and dashed lines, respectively) do not show substantial differences. Moreover, when they differ the distributed variants perform slightly better. To understand these two counterintuitive results, we analyze the achievable rate traces of the active users and the resource allocations obtained by the two schemes. Both schemes assign resources to a given user by prioritizing the time slots with higher achievable rate. However, the centralized scheme considers all users at the same time, while the distributed version optimizes each user separately. In order for the distributed solver to have the same performance of the centralized version, the resource allocations obtained for each user must be *compatible*. We call compatible a set of allocations that can be superimposed without creating any

Fig. 15. CDFs of the data rate increase obtained by anticipatory networking solutions for different prediction accuracies and for centralized and distributed schemes.

unfeasible condition (i.e., requiring more than the available resources in a given time slot). All the test cases analyzed in detail showed one of the two following outcomes. The first and more common situation is that all users have achievable rate peaks in different time slots so that their optimized allocations do not collide or, if they do, their combination does not exceed the available resources. The second situation, which occurs much more rarely, has two or more users showing simultaneous peaks of achievable rate and, thus, the resource allocations computed by the distributed solver collide in one or more time slots. These collisions reduce the amount of resources assigned to all users so that the service may be momentarily interrupted (i.e., outage). Since the distributed scheme trades some outage for some lower resource utilization, the performance of the centralized scheme seems worse.

Fig. 15 shows the CDF of the quality maximization performance and is equivalent to the previous in all aspects, but for the magnitude of the improvements. In fact, the quality maximization solutions are able to more than double the data rate for the downlink channel. Conversely, in the uplink (see the supplemental material) the improvements barely reach 40%. This disparity of performance is justified by the different MCS statistics of the downlink and uplink channels, of which the second is consistently higher. In turn, this translates into a smaller margin of optimization for the uplink data rates, as can be seen from Fig. 11(b) for a comparison of the MCS CDF and Fig. 12 for a detailed representation of MCS traces in both channels, where all

5. Uplink charts are provided as supplemental material.

Fig. 16. Anticipatory networking performance varying the prediction horizon length.

uplink traces are represented with lighter shades of gray (i.e., higher MCS). Overall, we measured data rate improvements between 20% and 100% with a median value of 65% for downlink communications and between 3% and 13% (median 6.5%) for the uplink. Again centralized and distributed schemes fare very similarly.

We also compare the CDFs of the two main metrics computed in each data set separately: the performance computed by our optimization framework does not differ by more than 5-10%, but for the Leganes data set, where the performance are uniformly 10% better than in the other data sets. We attribute this to the low load and mostly residential characteristics of this data set.

Fig. 16 shows the impact of the prediction horizon (i.e., represents the number of time slots optimized at once). Thus, a shorter horizon makes the optimizer less effective as it can only rely on short term information. On the other hand, a longer horizon increases the optimization complexity in terms of both memory and computation requirements. In the figure we show normalized average results in order to be able to compare solutions with different performance. The chosen examples consider a maximum prediction horizon of one minute and analyze the same by giving the optimizer a fraction of the whole available information. Although the best performance is reached asymptotically, substantial improvements can be obtained with just a few seconds of prediction and 90% of the maximum savings are achieved with a 10-second horizon. Results are shown for both the omniscient predictor (ideal, solid lines) and the reactive predictor (realistic, dashed lines).

This graph clarifies why the realistic predictors performs so closely to the omniscient one. In fact, reducing the prediction horizon of the omniscient predictor makes it similar to a realistic one which is more effective in the first time slots only. In our experiments a realistic (either proactive or reactive) predictor performed like an omniscient one with a horizon of about 10 seconds. Finally, we analyze the impact of buffer size on the optimization performance, Fig. 17 shows the normalized average improvements for the two metrics. The fraction of buffer given to each of the active users is proportional to the amount of requested data in the time frame. Thus, a 100% buffer would allow a user to prefetch everything at the beginning of the trace. While increasing the buffer size over 100% does not improve the resource savings, the data rate can be further increased by allowing the user to buffer more data. In particular, in our test conditions a buffer four times as large as the requested

Fig. 17. Anticipatory networking performance varying the buffer size.

data transfer allows for maximum performance gain⁶.

A few final considerations about the overall approach are in order. The first concerns our data sets: optimizing network resource allocation starting from real traces makes it impossible for the optimizer to run into infeasible conditions, because the starting point was already feasible. The second consideration concerns whether the anticipatory gains can be estimated from the trace characteristics without solving the optimization problem. Studying the correlation between our final results and the compound metrics computed above for active users we found they are almost independent. This is due to the fact that the degree of improvement does not depend on the characteristics of individual users, but on their combination. Determining whether combining different users results in a good mix and provides high gains is a problem just as complex as the resource allocation problem itself.

5 RELATED WORKS

In this section we discuss a few alternative approaches to our evaluation framework, alternative tools to record mobile network traffic and measurement-driven analysis of mobile networks. Yin et al. [25], [26] propose a throughput prediction solution based on clustering and hidden Markov models. Their predictor is subsequently used to control video bitrate selection in a multimedia streaming application. Similarly, Kurdoglu et al. [27] exploit an online linear adaptive filter to optimize the video bitrate thanks to future capacity prediction. Muppisetty et al. [28] investigate the spatial prediction of wireless channels using Gaussian processes. Atawia et al. [29] focus on energy savings obtained thanks to predictive resource allocation and uncertainty management. Also, Yu et al. [30] optimize energy consumption by means of predictive scheduling of multi-technology wireless networks (i.e., WiFi and cellular), which is based on Lyapunov optimization. More recently, Yue et al. [31] exploit machine learning to obtain accurate link bandwidth prediction.

Finally, Du et al. [32] design a predictive backpressure algorithm to solve the resource allocation problem for multimedia streaming. The framework described here is not

6. This is possible because the data rate maximization problem computes how much data could the users get using the same quantity of resources they used in the traces, but using the slots with the best communication quality. Thus, in order to achieve the maximum potential we have to allow their obtained data to exceed their requirements and, therefore, a buffer larger than the requirements might be needed

meant to provide a comprehensive overview of the topic, but allowed us to test the performance of several realistic approaches against theoretical bounds. Most of the literature on anticipatory networking, with only a few exceptions (e.g., [25]) evaluate their solutions on synthetic data sets.

When mobile operators disclose their data sets, very interesting and insightful papers originate. For instance, the recent works of Furno et al. [33], [34] study the influence of human activities on mobile communications and identify several traffic patterns that can be used to enhance anticipatory networking. In a similar fashion, two papers [8], [9] analyze the traffic in Shanghai and conclude that cell profiles exhibit high predictability in their “regular components”. In particular, [9] studies the network traffic predictability by means of temporal time-series. However, our analysis differs in that our prediction entails single users instead of the aggregate cell and it is performed on a different time scale (i.e., fractions of a second instead of minutes). The same data set is also analyzed by Ding et al [10] to model the network capability. Previous studies, such as those of Shafiq et al. [35], [36] and Keralapura et al. [37] investigate traffic profiles and their predictability. While our data sets are obtained by directly decoding the control channel of the eNodeB, alternative techniques, such as crowd-sourced data collection [38] can be used. Our approach is preferable to target specific location with high precision, while crowd-sourcing techniques are more appropriate to obtain data sets spanning very large geographic areas.

Different from all these studies, we collected our data set using our LTE sniffer [18] and our data set is available on request to the community to allow for comparative studies and the development of practical solutions. Our data set, which is intrinsically anonymous due to the use of temporary identifiers instead of unique user IDs, is also the only one to provide scheduling information at millisecond granularity. Thus, to the best of our knowledge, our data set is the only archive of fine-grained mobile network traffic obtained independently of mobile operators. Moreover, the tool used to obtain our data sets are publicly available⁷, to allow independent researchers to perform additional measurement campaigns and verify our findings.

Alternative free sniffers for mobile network traffic are available in the literature. Kumar et al. [24] proposed LTEye, which provided the inspiration for our tool, while Xie et al. [39] developed Rmon from which we adapted the technique to test OWL. A very recent solution is designed by Falkenberg et al. [40] to estimate mobile phone connectivity. MobileInsight [11] is another tool meant to obtain mobile network information from the UE perspective and is developed by Li et al. Of course, commercial products might offer similar features albeit at a much higher price and complexity, e.g., QXDM [41], Actix Analyzer [42], or TEMS investigation [43].

6 CONCLUSIONS

In this paper we conducted a performance evaluation of anticipatory networking solutions based on real world traffic measurements. In particular, we provided three main contributions: a large data set providing fine-grained scheduling

information of four cells around Madrid, a comprehensive framework to study realistic anticipatory networking solutions against their theoretical bounds and a thorough evaluation of these techniques on our data set.

We found that anticipatory optimization provides substantial resource savings and data rate enhancements. In the data set, more than 80% of the total traffic is produced by less than 30% of the users, which also exhibit the more predictable behaviors. Thus, by analyzing this predictable traffic component and considering the rest as inelastic background traffic, we obtained about 35% resource saving and double data rates in the downlink channel, while in the uplink channel lower gains are obtained due to the higher average MCS that is usually assigned in these communications.

We found that moving from an omniscient predictor to more realistic ones has a substantial impact on performance, while both proactive and reactive predictors achieved very similar performance. In addition, we found that in our data sets centralized and distributed approaches have very similar performance. This is due to the relatively low load of the cell in our data sets that very rarely cause multiple users to select the same time slot. Finally, we conclude that anticipatory networking is both a viable and effective solution that merits its place in 5G networks. On top of the performance improvement, it provides a new perspective on dealing with context information that the network can provide to mobile operators and application developers to enable future high rate services.

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